

RESEARCH ARTICLE

0-MODULAR SEMI LATTICES**S. S. Khopade¹ and S. P. Thorat²**¹Karmaveer Hire Arts, Science, Commerce and Education College,
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Kolhapur, M. S., India 416003.Corresponding author E-mail: santajikhopade@gmail.com, thoratsanjay15@gmail.comDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15833273>**Abstract:**

The concept of a 0-modular semilattice is introduced and some properties of 0-modular semilattices are proved. A necessary and sufficient condition for a 0 - modular,* - semilattice to be weakly distributive is established.

Keywords: Distributive Semilattice, 0- Distributive Semilattice, 0 - Modular Semilattice, Semi-Ideal.

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1. Introduction:

In their work, Gratzner and Schmidt [3] introduced the concept of distributive semilattices, while Frink [1] presented the idea of pseudo-complemented semilattices. Building on these concepts, Varlet [8] has defined and examined the properties of 0-distributive semilattice which is a generalization of distributive semilattices and pseudo-complemented semilattices. In [4], some properties of the annihilator semi-ideals in a meet semilattice are studied. Further, for a congruence relation R defined on a semilattice S with 0, by $x \equiv y(R) \Leftrightarrow \{x\}^* = \{y\}^*$ ($x, y \in S$), it is proved that the quotient semilattice $\langle S/R, \wedge \rangle$ is isomorphic with the semilattices $\langle S^{**}, \cap \rangle$ and $\langle \mathcal{K}, \cap \rangle$ where $S^{**} = \{\{x\}^{**} \mid x \in S\}$ and $\mathcal{K} = \{\{M\}_x \mid x \in S\}$, here $\{M\}_x = \{M \mid x \notin M, M \text{ is a minimal prime semi-ideal in } S\}$.

In this paper the concept of 0-modular semilattices is introduced as a generalization to modular semilattices first introduced by Rhodes [6]. We observe that almost all the results of section 2 in [5] can be extended to the more general class of modular semilattices.

2. Preliminaries:

This section provides an overview of established concepts and findings that will be utilized in the later sections. For fundamental concepts in lattice theory, the reader is directed to [2]. In this paper, we will

focus on the \wedge -semilattice $\langle S, \wedge \rangle$, which we will refer to simply as S . For definitions and symbols related to semilattices, we adhere to the references [4], [5] and [9].

In the semilattice S , the partial ordering \leq is defined by $a \leq b$ if and only if $a \wedge b = a$. The least element is represented by 0 , while the greatest element is represented by 1 , assuming they exist. A semilattice S is classified as bounded if both 0 and 1 are present in S . From this point forward, S will refer to a meet semilattice that includes 0 unless noted otherwise. For any non-empty subset A of S , the set $A^* = \{x \in S : x \wedge a = 0 \text{ for all } a \in A\}$ is called the annihilator of A .

Definition 1: “ S is said to be pseudo-complemented if for every $a \in S$ there exists $b \in S$ such that $\{a\}^* = \{b\}$. This b is called the pseudo-complement of a and is denoted by a^* ”.

Definition 2: “ S is said to be a $*$ - semilattice if for any $x \in S$ there exists $x' \in S$ such that $\{x\}^{**} = \{x'\}^{**}$ ”.

Definition 3: “ S is called a modular semi lattice if $x, y, z \in S$ and $x \geq y \wedge z$ imply the existence of $t, r \in S$ such that $x \wedge t = x \wedge r = t \wedge r$ ”.

Definition 4: “ S is said to be weakly distributive semilattice if $\{x\}^*$ is an ideal for any $x \in S$ ”.

Definition 5: “ S is called 0-distributive semilattice if A^* is an ideal for any non-empty subset A of S ”.

Definition 6: “ S is said to be disjunctive (weakly complemented) if for $a, b \in S$ and $a \not\leq b$ imply that there exists $c \in S$ such that $a \wedge c = 0$ but $b \wedge c \neq 0$ ”.

Definition 7: “ S is said to be dense if $(a)^* = \{0\}$ for all $0 \neq a \in S$ ”.

We collect below some notions and results from [4] that we need in further section.

Result 1: “ $\{a \wedge b\}^{**} = \{a\}^{**} \cap \{b\}^{**}$ for all $a, b \in S$ ”.

Result 2: Following properties hold in S for annihilator semi-ideals in S . Let A and B denote non-empty subsets of S .

- (1) $A^* = \bigcap \{\{a\}^* \mid a \in A\}$.
- (2) If $A \subseteq B$, then $B^* \subseteq A^*$ and $A^{**} \subseteq B^{**}$.
- (3) $A \subseteq A^{**}$.
- (4) $A^* = A^{***}$.
- (5) $A^* \subseteq B^* \Leftrightarrow B^{**} \subseteq A^{**}$.
- (6) $A^* \cap A^{**} = \{0\}$.
- (7) If I and J are semi-ideals then $I \cap J = \{0\} \Leftrightarrow I \subseteq J^*$.

Define a relation R on S as follows:

$$x \equiv y(R) \Leftrightarrow \{x\}^* = \{y\}^* \quad (x, y \in S).$$

Then R is a congruence relation on S . Therefore $S/R = \{[x]^R \mid x \in S\}$ and \wedge on S/R is defined by $[x]^R \wedge [y]^R = [x \wedge y]^R$, for $x, y \in S$. Thus, we have a \wedge - semilattice $\langle S/R, \wedge \rangle$.

Take $S^{**} = \{\{x\}^{**} \mid x \in S\}$. Then $\langle S^{**}, \cap \rangle$ is a semilattice.

Result 3: “For a semilattice S , $\langle S/R, \wedge \rangle$ is isomorphic with $\langle S^{**}, \cap \rangle$ ”.

Let \mathfrak{M} denote the set of all minimal prime semi-ideals of S .

Define $\mathcal{K} = \{\{M\}_x \mid x \in S\}$ where $\{M\}_x = \{M \in \mathfrak{M} \mid x \notin M\}$. Then $\langle \mathcal{K}, \cap \rangle$ is a semilattice.

Result 4: “For S , the semilattices $\langle S/R, \wedge \rangle$ and $\langle \mathcal{K}, \cap \rangle$ are isomorphic”.

Result 5: “For a semilattice S , the three semilattices $\langle S/R, \wedge \rangle$, $\langle \mathcal{K}, \cap \rangle$ and $\langle S^{**}, \cap \rangle$ are isomorphic”.

Let F be a filter in S . Then a relation $\theta(F)$ defined on S by

$$x \equiv y(\theta(F)) \Leftrightarrow x \wedge f = y \wedge f \text{ for some } f \in F$$

is a congruence relation on S .

3. 0 – modular semilattices

According to Rhodes [6], S is called a modular semilattice if $x, y, z \in S$ and $x \geq y \wedge z$ imply the existence of $t, r \in S$ such that $x \wedge t = x \wedge r = t \wedge r$.

As a generalization of this we define a 0 – modular semilattice as

Definition: A semilattice S with 0 is said to be 0 - modular if $x \wedge y = 0$ ($x, y \in S$), then for any $z \in S$, there exist $x_1 \geq x$ and $y_1 \geq y$ such that $y \wedge x_1 = y \wedge z$ and $x \wedge y_1 = x \wedge z$.

Theorem 3.1: Every modular semilattice with 0 is 0 - modular.

Proof: Let S be a modular semilattice with 0 and let $x \wedge y = 0$ ($x, y \in S$). Then for any $z \in S$, we get $0 = x \wedge y \leq y \wedge z$. As S is a modular semilattice, there exist $x_1 \geq x$ and $y_1 \geq y$ such that $x_1 \wedge y_1 = (y \wedge z) \wedge y_1 = (y \wedge z) \wedge x_1$. Hence $x_1 \wedge y_1 = y \wedge z = (y \wedge z) \wedge x_1$. Further

$$y \wedge x_1 = (y \wedge y_1) \wedge x_1 = y \wedge (y_1 \wedge x_1) = y \wedge (y \wedge z) = y \wedge z \text{ _____ (1)}$$

Again $0 = x \wedge y \leq x \wedge z$. As S is a modular semilattice, there exist $x_2 \geq x$ and $y_2 \geq y$ such that $x_2 \wedge y_2 = (x \wedge z) \wedge y_2 = (x \wedge z) \wedge x_2$. Hence $x_2 \wedge y_2 = (x \wedge z) \wedge y_2 = x \wedge z$. Again $x \wedge y_2 = (x \wedge x_2) \wedge y_2 = x \wedge (x_2 \wedge y_2) = x \wedge (x \wedge z) = x \wedge z$. Thus $x \wedge y = 0$ implies there exist $x_1 \geq x$ and $y_2 \geq y$ such that $y \wedge x_1 = y \wedge z$ and $x \wedge y_2 = x \wedge z$ for any $z \in S$. Hence S is a 0 – modular semilattice. ■

Let $D = \{x \in S : \{x\}^* = \{0\}\}$ denote the set of all dense elements in S . Henceforth we assume that $D \neq \emptyset$. Then D is a filter in S . Define a relation $\theta(D)$ on S by $x \equiv y(\theta(D)) \Leftrightarrow x \wedge d = y \wedge d$ for some $d \in D$. Then $\theta(D)$ is a congruence relation on S . In a 0 - modular, * - semilattice we have

Theorem 3.2: In a 0 - modular, * - semilattice S we have $\theta(D) = R$.

Proof: Let $x \equiv y(\theta(D))$. Then $x \wedge d = y \wedge d$ for some $d \in D$. But then $\{x \wedge d\}^{**} = \{y \wedge d\}^{**}$ implies $\{x\}^{**} \cap \{d\}^{**} = \{y\}^{**} \cap \{d\}^{**}$ (by Result 1). Hence $\{x\}^{**} = \{y\}^{**}$ (since $\{d\}^{**} = \{0\}$). Therefore, by Result 2 - (4), we get $\{x\}^* = \{y\}^*$. Thus $x \equiv y(R)$. This shows that $\theta(D) \leq R$ _____ (1)

Let $x \equiv y(R)$ then $\{x\}^* = \{y\}^* \Rightarrow \{x \wedge y\}^* = \{x\}^* = \{y\}^*$. As S is a * - semilattice there exists $x' \in S$ such that $\{x\}^{**} = \{x'\}^*$. As $y \in \{y\}^{**}$ we get $y \in \{x\}^{**}$. Hence $y \in \{x'\}^*$ implies $y \wedge x' = 0$. S being 0 - modular there exists $x_1 \geq x'$ such that $y \wedge x_1 = y \wedge x$. As $\{x \wedge y\}^{**} = \{x'\}^*$ we get $[x \wedge y] \cap [x'] \subseteq D$. Hence as $x_1 \geq x'$ and $x_1 \geq x \wedge y$, we get $x_1 \in D$. Similarly as $x \wedge x' = 0$, there exists $y_1 \geq x'$ such that $x \wedge y_1 = x \wedge y$. As $y_1 \geq y \wedge x$ and $y_1 \geq x'$ we get $y_1 \in D$. Thus we have $x \wedge y_1 = x \wedge y = x_1 \wedge y$ and $x_1 \wedge y_1 \in D$. Therefore $x \wedge (x_1 \wedge y_1) = y \wedge (x_1 \wedge y_1)$ implies $x \equiv y(\theta(D))$. This shows that $R \leq \theta(D)$. Combining both the inequalities we get $\theta(D) = R$. ■

As every modular semilattice with 0 is 0 - modular, we get the following.

Corollary 3.3: $\theta(D) = R$ in a modular $*$ -semilattice S ([5], Theorem 3).

Now we prove a lemma which is crucial for our next theorem.

Lemma 3.4: Let $a \in S$ be such that $\{a\}^{**} = \{a'\}^*$ for some $a' \in S$. Then following statements hold for any $x \in S$.

- (1) $x \wedge a' \equiv x(R)$ for each $x \in \{a\}^*$.
- (2) If $R = \theta(D)$, then $a' \in [x] \vee D$ for each $x \in \{a\}^*$.
- (3) If $R = \theta(D)$ and if D is neutral element of the lattice of all filters of S , then the semi-ideal $\{a\}^*$ is an ideal of S .

Proof:

(1) Let $x \in \{a\}^*$. Then $\{x\}^{**} \subseteq \{a\}^* = \{a'\}^{**}$. Claim that $\{x \wedge a'\}^* = \{x\}^*$. Let $t \in \{x \wedge a'\}^*$. Then $t \wedge x \wedge a' = 0 \Rightarrow t \wedge x \in \{a'\}^* = \{a\}^{**}$. Further $x \in \{a\}^* \Rightarrow t \wedge x \wedge a = 0 \Rightarrow t \wedge x \in \{a\}^*$. Thus $t \wedge x \in \{a\}^* \cap \{a\}^{**} = \{0\} \Rightarrow t \wedge x = 0 \Rightarrow t \in \{x\}^*$. Hence $\{x \wedge a'\}^* \subseteq \{x\}^*$. As $\{x \wedge a'\}^* \supseteq \{x\}^*$, we get $\{x \wedge a'\}^* = \{x\}^*$ for $x \in \{a\}^*$. Hence $x \wedge a' \equiv x(R)$.

(2) Let $R = \theta(D)$. Select any $x \in \{a\}^*$. Then by (1), $x \wedge a' \equiv x(R)$. Hence $x \wedge a' \equiv x(\theta(D))$ implies $x \wedge a' \wedge d = x \wedge d$ for some $d \in D$. But then $x \wedge d \in [x] \vee D$ will imply $x \wedge a' \wedge d \in [x] \vee D$. As $a' \geq x \wedge a' \wedge d$ we get $a' \in [x] \vee D$ and the result follows.

(3) $\{a\}^*$ is a semi-ideal of S . Let $x, y \in \{a\}^*$. By (2), $a' \in [x] \vee D$ and $a' \in [y] \vee D$. Hence $a' \in [[x] \vee D] \cap [[y] \vee D] \Rightarrow a' \in [[x] \cap [y]] \vee D$ (since D is a neutral element). Therefore $a' \geq z \wedge e$ for some $z \in [x] \cap [y]$ and $e \in D$. But then $z \wedge e \wedge a = 0 \Rightarrow z \wedge a \in \{e\}^* = \{0\}$ as $e \in D$. Hence $z \wedge a = 0 \Rightarrow z \in \{a\}^*$. Thus for $x, y \in \{a\}^*$, there exists $z \in \{a\}^*$ such that $z \geq x$ and $z \geq y$. This shows that $\{a\}^*$ is an ideal of S . ■

Now we prove a necessary and sufficient condition for a 0 - modular, $*$ - semilattice S to be weakly distributive in the following theorem.

Theorem 3.5: Let S be a 0 - modular, $*$ - semilattice. S is weakly distributive if and only if D is a neutral element of the lattice of all filters of S .

Proof: Only if part: It is enough to prove that $[[x] \vee D] \cap [[y] \vee D] = [[x] \cap [y]] \vee D$ for any $x, y \in S$. Note that $[[x] \cap [y]] \vee D \subseteq [[x] \vee D] \cap [[y] \vee D]$ always. Let $t \in [[x] \vee D] \cap [[y] \vee D]$. Then $t \geq x \wedge d_1$ and $t \geq y \wedge d_2$ for some $d_1, d_2 \in D$. But then $t \geq x \wedge d$ and $t \geq y \wedge d$ where $d = d_1 \wedge d_2 \in D$. As S is $*$ -semilattice $\{t\}^{**} = \{t'\}^*$ for some $t' \in S$. As $\{t\}^{**}$ is a semi-ideal of S , $x \wedge d, y \wedge d \in \{t\}^{**} = \{t'\}^*$ and hence $x, y \in \{t'\}^*$ as $d \in D$. S being weakly distributive, $\{t'\}^*$ is an ideal of S and hence there exists $z \in \{t'\}^*$ such that $z \geq x$ and $z \geq y$. As $\{t\}^* = \{t'\}^{**}$ by Lemma 3.4 (1) we get $z \wedge t \equiv z(R)$. As $R = \theta(D)$ by Theorem 3.2, $z \wedge t \wedge e = z \wedge e$ for some $e \in D$. As $z \in [x] \cap [y]$, we have $z \wedge e \in [[x] \cap [y]] \vee D$. As $t \geq z \wedge t \wedge e = z \wedge e$ we get $t \in [[x] \cap [y]] \vee D$. This shows that $[[x] \vee D] \cap [[y] \vee D] \subseteq [[x] \cap [y]] \vee D$.

$[[y] \vee D] \subseteq [[x] \cap [y]] \vee D$. Combining both the inclusions we get $[[x] \vee D] \cap [[y] \vee D] = [[x] \cap [y]] \vee D$.

If part: By Theorem 3.2, S being a 0-modular, $*$ - semilattice $\theta(D) = R$. As S is a $*$ - semilattice, for each $a \in S$, there exists $a' \in S$ such that $\{a\}^{**} = \{a'\}^*$. Hence by Lemma 3.4 (3), $\{a\}^*$ is an ideal of S for each $a \in S$. Hence S is weakly distributive. ■

Remark: The above theorem is a generalization of the following result of Murty ([3], Corollary 1): “Let S be a modular, $*$ - semilattice. Then S is weakly distributive if and only if $D \neq \emptyset$ is a neutral element of S ”.

A necessary and sufficient condition for a 0 – modular semilattice to be a $*$ - semilattice is proved in the following theorem.

Theorem 3.6: Let S be a 0 – modular semilattice. Then S is a $*$ - semilattice if and only if $S/\theta(D)$ is a pseudo-complemented semilattice.

Proof: Only if part:

Let S be a 0 - modular, $*$ - semilattice. As S is a $*$ - semilattice, S^{**} is a pseudo-complemented semilattice. Further $S/R \cong S^{**}$ (see Theorem 3.5) will imply S/R is a pseudo-complemented semilattice. As S is a 0 - modular, $*$ - semilattice, $R = \theta(D)$ (see Theorem 3.2). Hence, we get $S/\theta(D)$ is a pseudo-complemented semilattice.

If part:

Let S be a 0 - modular semilattice such that the semilattice $S/\theta(D)$ is pseudo-complemented. To prove that S is a $*$ - semilattice. Let $[x]^{\theta(D)} \in S/\theta(D)$ for $x \in S$. By assumption $[[x]^{\theta(D)}]^*$ exists in $S/\theta(D)$ and let $[[x]^{\theta(D)}]^* = [y]^{\theta(D)}$. Claim that $\{x\}^* = \{y\}^{**}$.
 $[x]^{\theta(D)} \cap [y]^{\theta(D)} = [0]^{\theta(D)} \Rightarrow [x \wedge y]^{\theta(D)} = [0]^{\theta(D)} \Rightarrow x \wedge y \wedge d = 0$ for some $d \in D$. Hence $x \wedge y \in \{d\}^* = \{0\} \Rightarrow x \wedge y = 0$. Thus $y \in \{x\}^* \Rightarrow \{y\}^{**} \subseteq \{x\}^*$. To prove $\{x\}^* \subseteq \{y\}^{**}$. Let $r \in \{x\}^*$ and $t \in \{y\}^*$. Now $[r]^{\theta(D)} \cap [x]^{\theta(D)} = [r \wedge x]^{\theta(D)} = [0]^{\theta(D)}$ which implies $[r]^{\theta(D)} \subseteq [[x]^{\theta(D)}]^* = [y]^{\theta(D)}$. But then $r \in [y]^{\theta(D)} \Rightarrow r \equiv y(\theta(D)) \Rightarrow r \wedge d = y \wedge d$ for some $d \in D$. Therefore $r \wedge t \wedge d = y \wedge t \wedge d = 0 \Rightarrow r \wedge t \in \{d\}^* = \{0\} \Rightarrow r \wedge t = 0$. But this shows that $r \in \{y\}^{**}$. Therefore $\{x\}^* \subseteq \{y\}^{**}$. Combining both the inclusions, we get $\{x\}^* = \{y\}^{**}$ and hence S is a $*$ - semilattice. ■

Applying Theorem 3.2 and Theorem 3.6 we get the following.

Corollary 3.7: In a 0 – modular semilattice $*$ - semilattice S/R is a pseudo -complemented semilattice

Remark: The above Theorem 3.6 is a generalization of the following theorem of Murty ([4], Corollary 2): “ S is a modular semilattice with $D \neq \emptyset$, then S is a $*$ - semilattice if and only if $S/\theta(D)$ is a pseudo-complemented semilattice”.

A generalization of Theorem 6 in [5] is obtained in the following theorem.

Theorem 3.8: For a 0 - modular * - semilattice S with 1, the following statements are equivalent.

- (1) S is a Boolean algebra.
- (2) S is a (weakly complemented) disjunctive semilattice.
- (3) $D = \{1\}$.

Proof: (1) \Rightarrow (2) is obviously true.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) follows by Theorem 6 in [9].

(3) \Rightarrow (1):

By Theorem 3.6, the semilattice $S/\theta(D)$ is pseudo-complemented. As $D = \{1\}$, we get $S/\theta(D) \cong S$.

Hence S is pseudo-complemented. As S is a pseudo-complemented, *- semilattice we have S is a Boolean algebra (see Frink [1]). Hence the implication. ■

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